

E-TAXATION AND REVENUE GENERATION IN ENUGU STATE: THE SUSTAINABILTY QUESTIONS

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Keywords: <i>e-Taxation, e-Governance, Tax compliance and Consolidated revenue system</i>	Abstract: <i>The study is anchored on e-taxation and revenue generation in Enugu State, with special regards to consolidation and sustainability. The period under study is 2015-2025. The objectives of the study were to access the effects of e-taxation on consolidated revenue system in Enugu State and secondly ascertain the effects of e-taxation on tax compliance in Enugu State. A descriptive survey research method was adopted, while the population of the study consist of taxpayers, financial inspectorates, treasury department, sub-treasuries, revenue headquarters, and ministry of finance, which is 11,372, cutting across the three senatorial zones of the State. Meanwhile the sample size is 588 using Taro Yamani statistical formular. The the study employed a combination of stratified random sampling and purposive to guarantee that each stratum is adequately represented in the sample. Based on the findings the study revealed that e-taxation has no significant positive effect on consolidated tax systems. That e-taxation has significant positive effect on tax compliance rates among taxpayers. It recommends that a comprehensive awareness campaign should be launched to educate taxpayers on the benefits, procedures and usage of e-taxation platform, as well implement a robust cybersecurity framework to safeguard taxpayers' data.</i>
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Introduction

1. Background of the Study

Cost of governance in terms of revenue generation has left various State governments in Nigeria with formulation of strategies to boast revenue base. E-taxation is an off shoot of E-Governance, which enhances ease of doing business. E-governance refers to the use of

information and communication technology (ICT) by government institutions to enhance service delivery, improve administrative functions and increase transparency and accountability. (Heeks, 2016; Bwalya & Mutula, 2016). One of the areas where e-governance has been implemented is in revenue generation, via e-tax system. Thus, the intergration of e-

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governance tools into revenue generation system has been a strategy to improve efficiency, reduce corruption, minimize errors and streamline process (Olatunji, 2019). Fatile, (2022) sees e-governance in the context of revenue generation as involving the use of digital platform for task such as tax filing, payment processing and management of tax payer's data, hence e-taxation.

It is an indisputable fact that the revenue generation of most government in Nigeria is far below what it should be (Adeboye, 2019). The effects of poor revenue generation is that inadequate finance remains the most single devastating challenge undermining effective State government administration in Nigeria. Enugu State is known to be one of the States that receives the least allocation from the federal account. The internally generated revenue (IGR) of the State has been very low when compared with other States in the region. That notwithstanding, the State has recorded marginal growth in IGR over the last few years, with records of leakages, which still makes it difficult for them to reach optimum potentials. Irrespective of the percentage increase in IGR in the State, they are yet meet up with their statutory infrastructural development and other pressing development needs.

The State's poor IGR performance has become a major obstacles to the development agenda of successive administration in the State, having great constrained annual budget. However, several reports identified lack of financial and administrative autonomy for the State Board of Internal Revenue (ESBIRS), poor taxpayers

data base, lack of automation of the database, functional process, weak personal structure in terms of skills and remuneration and inadequate logistics as a major factor that presently limit the performance of the State Board of Internal Revenue Services, which to a large extent is responsible for poor development in the State, (Obi & Okafor, 2019). The Board is saddled with the responsibility of driving and generating the said revenue, but seems incapacitated in terms of generation and drive.

The rise of e-governance has significantly transformed the way Government interact with citizens (G2C), business (G2B) and Government (G2G). As a result there is the resultant efficiency in service delivery of government agencies and the State revenue board. In 2015, electronic - taxation (e - taxation) was introduced by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). However, the digital platform was introduced to automate tax collection and drive to improve record keeping and facilitate better communication between the government and tax payers, though this have thrived with several challenges. This includes the inadequacy of infrastructures, the lack of sufficient technical expertise among staff and limited public awareness of the available e-tax services. Meanwhile, there are concerns about data security, system integration issues and resistance to change from both employees of the board and taxpayers, which may undermine the effectiveness of the implementation of e-taxation initiatives in the State. The effectiveness of e-taxation in enhancing the performance of State

Eneh Maximus Ikenna and Eze Chukwukadibia Chimauzom

board of internal revenue, remains unclear, particularly regarding its effects on revenue generation, tax compliance and overall efficiency. Hence, the need to evaluate how this digital tool have influenced the operational processes, transparency, financial performance of the board and general development of the State.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The broad objectives of the study is to examine the effects of e-taxation on revenue generation in Enugu State, while specific objective are:

1. To access the effects of e-taxation on consolidated revenue system in Enugu State
2. To ascertain the effects of e-governance on tax compliance in Enugu State.

1.3. Research Hypotheses

1. e-Taxation has significant positive effect on consolidated revenue system
2. e-Taxation has significant positive effect on tax compliance in Enugu State

2. Review of Related Literature

Concept of e-Taxation

E-taxation is seen as a system of administering tax online through electronic devices, Okoye & Ezejiofor (2014). Therefore, digitalization of tax

administration towards enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. The concept of e-tax system became a global phenomenon over 50 years ago and since then various governments of the world have adopted it to aid their tax generation machinery (Cobham, 2010). E-taxation involves filling tax returns electronically, get assessment done and communicated electronically as well as payment of tax online through the individual or business bank accounts (FIRS, 2021). The term "e-taxation" describes how governments administer and collect taxes by using digital technology and the internet. It refers to a set of electronic processes and systems meant to help individuals, businesses, and other entities comply with, report on, and pay taxes (Akadakpo & Imonitie, 2024).

Thus, it refers to the electronic filing and payment of taxes, using online platform and system. It streamlines the process for both actors (Taxpayers and Tax authorities), enhancing efficiency and accuracy. Therefore, e-taxation simplifies the tax process, fostering compliance and allowing tax authorities to manage collections more effectively.

Fig:1

Authors Compliation, 2026

e-taxation is anchored on the above key concepts, such as **e-filing**; which is the digital platform where taxpayers processes their tax returns in real time, without stress. While, **e-payment** allows taxpayer for easy and accessible process using designated digital paltform to effect payment from their confort zones. Hence, it is **real time** facilitated, whereby confirmation or refund is done as the case may be, the process ensures effective and efficient process at record time. Meanwhile, e-taxation ensures **data security**, using such measures as encryption to protect taxpayers information. **Accountability** is more of a life wire of every government, thus boasting taxpayers trust and enhancing improved compliance. **Accessibilty**, makes it convenient for taxpayers to effect payment. There is the exitence of built in **calculators** (automated), which is automated to eliminate

cases of human errors, while computing tax rates. However, e-taxation makes easy for taxpayers as they are regularly updated, leading to greater **compliance**. Finally, it made it possible for **support and resources**, on issues of confusion, there are platforms for tutorial, questions and answer, for clarity of doubts etc. Therefore, it is imperative to state that e-taxation system, records all transactions and stores them electronically, making easier to track and monitor activities.

Tax Compliance

Tax compliance refers to the degree to which individuals, businesess and organisations follow the tax laws and regulations set by the government, without default. It involves the timely and accurate reporting of income, the correct payment of tax owned and adherence to tax rules and regulations. Tax compliance is said to be the willingness of taxpayers to act in accordance with tax laws and fulfill their tax

Eneh Maximus Ikenna and Eze Chukwukadibia Chimauzom

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obligations voluntarily. Tax compliance encompasses accurate reporting in income, correct computation of tax liabilities, timely filing of returns, and prompt payment of dues (OECD, 2023). According to Alm (1991) he distinguished between voluntary and enforced compliance, highlighting the psychological and enforcement dimensions. Types of compliance according to the study includes:

a). Voluntary Compliance: When taxpayers willingly comply with tax laws without direct enforcement by tax officers or tax authorities.

b). Enforced Compliance: Compliance that results from audits, penalties, or legal actions taken by tax officers to compel payment and filing. To a large extent the taxpayer is under compulsion to do the needful.

c). Administrative Compliance: Following rules related to registration, documentation and timely filing of tax returns.

e). Technical Compliance: Accurate calculation and payment of the right amount of tax.

e-Taxation and Tax Compliance

Tax compliance is a critical issue for government globally, as it directly affects revenue generation and the State capacity to fund essential public services. To address compliance challenges, governments have increasingly adopted e-taxation system using digital technologies to facilitate public administration, enhance tax compliance rates (OECD, 2017; Akinwale, 2018).

Tax compliance, is seen as the degree to which taxpayers follow tax laws and regulations by submitting their returns and making payments accurately and in real time (Kirchler, 2017). E-taxation systems aim to improve tax

compliance by simplifying administrative procedure, enhancing transparency, and facilitating greater interaction between tax authorities and the public (Olatunji, 2019). Key components of e-taxation systems that promote higher compliance includes: E-filing,- digital submission of tax returns; e-payment,- an online systems for paying taxes; Taxpayer registration,- this is the digital platform for obtaining Tax Identification Numbers (TIN) and also managing taxpayer data; Automation of assessments, which includes use of ICT to calculate tax obligations, reducing human error and discretion; Information Availability, provides an online access to tax related information, deadline and procedural requirements to support taxpayer understanding and compliance (OECD, 2018). These digital tools are designed to reduce the complexities of tax processes, increase taxpayer satisfaction and ultimately encourage voluntary compliance with tax obligation (Akinwale, 2018; FIRS, 2020). Digital technologies and services are fundamental to tax administration, the extent to which they are adopted depends on the types of taxes administered and the development levels of the respective countries (Nose & Mengistu, 2023; Oladele et al, 2020).

The major imports of e-taxation on tax compliance rates are improved accessibility and convenience on the part of taxpayers. The digital systems makes it easier for taxpayers to comply with tax obligations by enabling an online filing and payment. The simplification of the process, along with automated reminder and easy access to tax information encourages

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taxpayers to file on real time, such as in India and South Africa etc (OECD, 2017). Meanwhile, the system is user friendly interface and mobile application made easier for businesses and individuals to file tax, leading to greater compliance (Murunga & Mwanja, 2020).

Secondly is reduction of errors, traditional tax filing system are often complex and prone to human errors. Digital platform through automation, reduces these assumed errors by automatically calculating tax liabilities and providing instant feedback to taxpayers. Automated system checks inconsistencies and errors before submissions are finalized, reducing the error margin. This electronic platform (e-taxation) has improved accuracy in tax returns, real time payment, leading to more reliable compliance.

Thirdly, it will enhance transparency and trust, e-taxation, enhances transparency and trust in the system. A situation where taxpayers can see, monitor the entire process of their tax filings and payment online, they are more likely to believe in the system and that their contributions are being properly utilized. OECD (2017) argued that transparency in e-taxation leads to increased trust, which is directly correlated with greater compliance rate.

Lastly, it improves behavioral change and perception of fairness, when taxpayers feel that the tax process is fair, transparent and easy to comply with, they are more likely to follow through with their obligations. O'Geil (2017) maintained that when tax system are perceived as equitable and well managed, voluntary

compliance increases, an example is Singapore's e-tax system, which has been credited with fostering a sense of fairness among taxpayers. As a result, compliance rates are consistently on the increase. The country's reputation for efficient public service delivery also enhances the legitimacy of the tax system, leading to increased willingness to comply.

Consolidated Tax System

A consolidated tax system generally refers to a method where various taxes that would otherwise be handled separately are merged into a single tax structure. This system can simplify tax administration, reduce compliance costs, and improve trust and efficiency in tax collection. OECD (2021), stated that tax compliance encompasses accurate reporting of income, correct computation of tax liabilities, timely filing of returns, and prompt payment of dues. There are a few contexts in which the term consolidated tax system can apply, especially when discoursing corporate taxation or income taxes. Alm (1991) distinguished between voluntary and enforced compliance, highlighting the psychological and enforcement dimensions.

Consolidated tax system can as well be seen as a framework where various taxes are integrated or harmonized under a unified system. This simply enhances the tax structure by reducing redundancies and overlapping tax categories, thereby improving efficiency in tax administration and enhancing overall revenue collection (Adebayo, 2019; Ofoegbu & Chukwuma, 2020). The Nigerian tax system reforms programme initiated by the federal Government has been a critical element in

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moving towards a consolidated tax system. Consolidated tax system involves an integrated framework of taxation that streamlines various types of taxes under a single system for easier administration, compliance and enforcement (Adeleke & Bello; Nwankwo, 2019). The idea is to streamline taxes at the federal, state and local government levels, to promote ease of doing businesses and reduce administrative burdens (FIRS, 2021; Onwuka, 2018), some reforms towards a consolidated system includes, Unified tax identification number and Digital tax system

Unified tax identification number (TIN) means to easily track and minimize the chances of tax evasion and avoidance by tax authorities from states or federal government (FIR, 2021). Meanwhile, how do this apply in the informal sector? Especially individual businesses that has no business with the banks or even government agencies.

Digital tax system is aimed at intergrating the entire tax administration process, which includes e-filing, and e-payment system by Nigerian revenue service (NRS) at the federal level and State board of internal revenue (SIRS) for transparency and accountability (Onwuka, 2018; Ofoegwu & Chukwuma, 2020).

In the context of Nigeria, the need for tax reform, simplification, and a consolidated tax system has gained significant attention, especially with the growing challenges in revenue generation and economic diversification (Ezeani & Okonkwo, 2021; Ojo, 2018). There exist various aspects of Nigeria's tax system, focusing on efforts towards

consolidation, impact of such system on tax compliance and the broader economic implications (Adeleke & Bello, 2020; Ezeani & Okonkwo, 2021). The Nigerian tax system is multi-tiered, involving federal, state and local government taxes, The Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS), now known as Nigerian Revenue Services (NRS, 2025) is responsible for administering federal taxes, while State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) manages taxes at the state level. Local government also impose certain taxes such as tenement rates and development levies (Olowookere & Oloniran, 2019; Nwankwo, 2020). The types of existing taxes in Nigeria are: Corporate Income Tax (CIT); Personal Income Tax (PIT); Value Added Tax (VAT); Education Tax; Withholding Tax (WHT); Stamp Duties Tax (Adeniran & Salawu, 2021). The multiplicity, duplication and recycling of taxes and the decentralized nature of administration can create challenges in terms of efficiency, compliance and enforcement. These complexities provides the rational for a consolidated or harmonized tax system that could ease tax collection, increase compliance and improve overall revenue generation (Okoye & Eze, 2022; Ogbonna & Appah, 2019).

Emerging Challenges of Nigeria's Tax System

Nigeria, has all it takes, to develop and improve the condition of living of her populace using internally generated revenue, but there are lots of bottle neck and challenges;

1. Tax evasion and non compliance: A significant emerging challenge is the high level of tax evasion. The lack of clear and unified tax

Eneh Maximus Ikenna and Eze Chukwukadibia Chimauzom

system makes it easier for taxpayers to evade certain taxes. The informal sector, which constitutes a large part of Nigeria's economy is particularly resistant to formal tax compliance (Onwudiwe, 2020; Udeh & Nnadi, 2019).

2. Weak enforcement mechanism: Even with the introduction of digital systems and reforms, enforcement of tax compliance remains a challenge. The lack of effective monitoring and punitive measures results in many businesses and individuals failing to comply with their tax obligations (Ogbonna & Appah, 2019; Olowookere & Olaniran, 2019).

3. Multiplicity of taxes: Nigeria's tax system is often seen as overly complex, with taxes levied at multiple levels of government, federal, state and local. This fragmentation leads to inefficiencies, including multiple tax payments for the same business transaction, confusion among tax payers and difficulties in enforcement (Akanbi & Aladejana, 2018; Okoye & Eze, 2022).

4. Inconsistent tax policies: Nigeria's tax policies are not always consistent across states creating discrepancies in tax rates, management and administration. This lack of uniformity hinders businesses that operates across state lines, as they must navigate a patchwork of state tax regulations (Nwankwo, 2020; Adeniran & Salawu, 2021).

5. Corruption and mismanagement of funds: Corruption at various quarters has hindered the effective administration of the tax system. Even if taxes are collected, the improper use or mismanagement of tax revenue remains a significant concern in Nigeria

(Adeboyin & Adekanmi, 2016; Dauda & Saidu, 2024).

e-Taxation and Consolidated Revenue

The adoption of digital tax system has been recognized globally as a transformative approach for improving tax administration and management. In Nigeria, the implementation of e-taxation has the potentials to enhance the efficiency, transparency and effectiveness of the tax system. By minimizing human interaction, digital platform reduces corruption, fraud and inefficiencies. Okonjo-Iweala & Osafo-Kwaako (2017) emphasize that e-taxation, online payment and digital records significantly enhances transparency and revenue tracking. Adeyemo (2021) maintained that the introduction of e-payment system in Nigeria led to an increase in tax compliance and revenue receipts. This adoption of electronic tax filing and assessment has reduced manual processes that often results in leakages.

In Enugu State, e-taxation has been partially adopted in key revenue generating agencies, for instance Enugu State Board of Internal Revenue Services (ESBIRS). The launch of an online tax portal has enabled businesses, individual and corporate bodies to process payment digitally. However, Eze & Chukwu (2022) observed that despite these efforts, challenges such as poor internet infrastructure, limited digital literacy, and resistance from revenue officers have hindered the system's full potentials. Meanwhile, Ogechukwu (2020) observed that while ICT tools have reduced

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physical interactions and improved record-keeping, the lack of comprehensive integration across ministries limits the impact on revenue generation.

2.2 Theoretical Foundation

The theoretical foundation adopted by the study is primarily based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), is a framework used to understand how users come to accept and use technology. It was developed by Fed Davis in 1986 and since then has become the most influential models for understanding technology in various contexts, especially in information system and technology research. The theory suggested user's acceptance (PU) of technology is influence by two main factors, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (PEOU). The TAM posits that the adoption and use of new technology, such as e-taxation, is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. This theory suggests that if taxpayers and tax authorities perceive e-taxation as useful and easy to use, they are more likely to accept, adapt and adopt it, leading to improved tax administration and compliance (Davis, 1989).

Perceived usefulness (PU), comes to terms with tax authorities and tax payers believing that the online tax system improves efficiency, which then translate to acceptability, adaptability and adoption. However, tax officers tends to appreciates e-filing which reduces the burden of manual work as well as errors, in making e-taxation hands-on solution. The extent to which e-taxation systems are viewed as capable of enhancing revenue collection, reducing

administrative burdens, and simplifying tax processes (Liao & Lu, 2022). E-taxation when accepted by both actors, the tax administrators and the taxpayers will enhance productivity in a successful progression, likewise when it becomes part of the people, (adaptability) and lastly, adopted by the Government of the State, for transparency and accountability.

Perceived ease of use (PEOU), exposes the extent to which a person believes using a system will be progressive, thus these factors influences users' attitude towards use, which affects behavioural intention to use, ultimately determining actual system usage. The degree of user-friendliness and compatibility with existing tax infrastructure, minimizing disruption to government workflows (Cengaver & Sesen, 2022). Taxpayers do not evade tax as a result of insensitivity but because of the attitude of tax administrators, who represents the Government and on the long run abuse of public funds. Unlike e-taxation, which is communicated and adopted over time within a social system, is poised to have relative advantage, transparent, reliable, accessible and compatible, etc. Other dimensions includes, trialability and observation of benefits.

Trialability, enhance governments ability to pilot e-taxation systems on a smaller scale before widespread implementation, managing risks associated with large-scale technological changes (Morris et al., 1995). It is more like pre-text program, reducing wastage at the verge of implementation. At this point some ministries or departments can be sampled, to ascertain the workability of the process.

Observability of benefits, this offer potential

Eneh Maximus Ikenna and Eze Chukwukadibia Chimauzom

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benefits for governments, when e-taxation system applies, ranging from increased tax compliance and improved revenue generation (Premkumar & Davis, 1996). These positions e-taxation more lucrative, attractive to policymakers, encouraging its acceptability, adaptability and adoption.

2.3 Empirical Review

Studies have been conducted to examine the relation between e-taxation and revenue collection, however, this study provides valuable insight on e-taxation and revenue generation in Enugu State. Critically looking at the area of digital technology in enhance revenue generation, through improved tax administration that translates to tax compliance, transparency and accountability.

Nwankwo (2020) conducted a study on the effectiveness of e-taxation on State-level revenue performance in Enugu State using time series regression model between 2012 to 2019. The study found that the adoption of e-taxation system improved turnaround time, accuracy and tax generation. The researcher attributed the improvement to reduced human interface, faster processing time and enhanced taxpayer record management.

Eze and Ugwoke (2023) carryout a research on the effects of e-governance reforms on revenue services in Enugu State Board of internal revenue services using mixed-method approach. The study revealed that e-governance tools significantly improved operational efficiency and increased voluntary compliance among informal sector taxpayers. The researchers also noted improvements in data accuracy, reduction in administrative costs and

increased stakeholders trust.

In the study conducted by Olatunji and Ayodele (2017), they examined the impact of information technology on tax administration in South West, Nigeria. However, the study conducted was to investigate the effect of information technology on tax implementation and planning. The study employed primary system of data collection through the means of structured questionnaires, while multiple regression and Pearson product moment correlation were used to analyze the data. The study revealed that information technology enhance the level of tax productivity and administration.

Asomba, Madunezim & Azubuike (2023), conducted a study on E-tax compliance in Nigeria, implication for company income tax and petroleum profit tax. The study observed that there exists a positive and insignificant variation in the revenue collected from capital gains tax before and after the implementation of e-taxation in Nigeria. However, there is a positive and insignificant difference in the Petroleum Profit Tax between the pre-and post-e-taxation periods. The study concluded that Nigeria's move to electronic tax compliance was inspired by the country's need for increased revenue generation, efficiency, and transparency. Thus, e-taxation system have improved the process of tax assessment and payment and enhanced the government's capacity to oversee and retrieve revenues from taxpayers.

3. Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research method, which focuses on the targeted

Eneh Maximus Ikenna and Eze Chukwukadibia Chimauzom

audience, It was adopted because the problem under study demanded the information as the principal means of data collection. The population of the study consist of taxpayers, financial inspectorates, treasury department, sub-treasuries, revenue headquarters, and ministry of finance, which is 11,372, cutting across the three senatorial zones of the State. Meanwhile the sample size is 588 using Taro Yamani statistical formular.

The the study employed a combination of stratified random sampling and purposive to guarantee that each stratum is adequately represented in the sample.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

What is the effect of e-Taxation on consolidated revenue system?

Mean rating of the respondents on the effects of e-taxation on consolidated revenue system.

Table 1

s / n	Items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	FR EQ	Me an	Decisi on
1	A unified digital system enables revenue board to maintain a comprehensive database for taxpayers.	55 29%	77 40%	25 13%	21 11%	18 9%	58 0	3.6 5	Accept ed
2	Consolidated revenue system identifies and eliminate redundant taxes, double taxation and tax evasion.	63 33%	58 30%	24 13%	24 13%	23 12%	58 0	3.8 0	Accept ed
3	Digital consolidation improves audit trails and visibility, fostering accountability.	65 34%	59 31%	21 11%	27 14%	20 10%	58 0	3.6 5	Accept ed
4	Consolidated tax system enhances analysis, forecasting and aid budgeting processes	61 32%	59 31%	27 14%	23 12%	22 11%	58 0	3.5 9	Accept ed
5	e-taxation platform enhances the consolidation of tax records from various government departments.	65 34%	59 31%	21 11%	27 14%	20 10%	58 0	3.6 5	Accept ed
	Grand Mean							3.8 0	

Field survey, 2025

Table 1 questionnaire items, 1,2,3,4, and 5 have a mean scores of 3.65, 3.80, 3.65, 3.59 and 3.65 which are above the average mean of 3.0. This is an indication that the following listed questionnaire item are the various effects of e-taxation on consolidated revenue system in Enugu State. The cluster of mean $3.70 > 3.00$ (Likert mean) and associated standard deviation of $1.16 < 1.1581$ (Likert standard deviation) indicates that e-taxation has no significant positive effect on consolidated tax system in Enugu State.

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Test statistics: One sample $t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}} = 47.26$, P-value = 0.0000

Table 2

s/n	Items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	FRE Q	Mean	Decision
1	Digital automated system reduces suspicion and enhances taxpayers confidence.	61 32%	59 31%	27 14%	23 12%	22 11%	580	3.59	Accepted
2	e-taxation system, sends automated alerts to tax payers for due date and penalties, making them stay informed	65 34%	59 31%	21 11%	27 14%	20 10%	580	3.65	Accepted
3	e-taxation system, reduces bureaucratic complexities.	63 33%	58 30%	24 13%	24 13%	23 12%	580	3.80	Accepted
4	e-taxation platforms makes it easier for taxpayers to register, do file returns and make online payments	65 34%	59 31%	21 11%	27 14%	20 10%	580	3.65	Accepted

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if \leq p-value 0.05, otherwise do not reject OR reject H_0 if the calculated value $>$ the critical table value, otherwise, do not reject.

Interpretation: The one-sample t-test result with t-statistics value of 47.26 and associated probability value of $0.0000 < 0.005$ reveals e-taxation has no significant positive effect on consolidated tax system in Enugu State.

How has e-taxation enhanced tax compliance in Enugu State

Mean rating of the respondents on how e-taxation enhanced tax compliance in Enugu State.

5	e-taxation initiatives involves public awareness campaign and feedback mechanism, fostering participation and compliance.	55 29%	77 40%	25 13%	21 11%	18 9%	580	3.65	Accepted
	Grand Mean							3.80	

Field survey, 2025

From table 2, questionnaire items, 1,2,3,4 and 5 have a mean score of 3.59, 3.65,3.80, 3.65, 3.65 and 3.65, which are above the average mean of 3.0. This is an indication that the following listed questionnaire item are the various effects that enhances tax compliance rate among tax payers in Enugu State. The cluster mean of $3.80 > 3.00$ (Likert mean) and associated standard deviation of $1.11 < 1.1581$ (Likert standard deviation) indicates that e-taxation has significant positive effect on tax compliance rate among taxpayers in Enugu State.

Level significance (α) = 0.05

Test statistics: One sample $t = x - u_0 = 40.89$, P-value = 0.0000

Interpretation: The one-sample t-test result with t-statistics value of 40.89 and associated probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$ reveals that e-taxation has significant positive effect on tax compliance rate among taxpayers in Enugu State.

Discussion of findings

The findings from the study provided valuable insights into the relationship between e-taxation initiatives and revenue generation in Enugu State, particularly in the domain of

revenue drive, collection, tax compliance and consolidated revenue system in Enugu State.

e-Taxation and Consolidated Revenue System

The study revealed that e-taxation has no significant positive effect on consolidated tax system in Enugu State. This suggests fragmentation in tax administration persists despite digital interventions. A consolidated tax system requires interoperability between different revenue streams and administrative units, unified databases, and standardized processes, which may not yet be fully operational within the State revenue circle. The lack of a cohesive digital framework may limit the ability to achieve full integration and transparency, affecting the overall effectiveness of tax administration. Meanwhile, the idea of billing criteria is a major flaw, it could be over or under billing which is always a major concern of the tax payers.

e-Taxation and Tax Compliance

Conversely, the study revealed a significant positive effect of e-taxation on tax compliance rates among taxpayers in Enugu State. This suggests that digital platforms have made it easier for taxpayers to access tax information, file returns and make payments, thereby improving voluntary compliance. The

convenience, transparency, and perceived reduction in human errors, brought about by e-taxation tools which is likely to contribute to this improved compliance. This findings aligns with the broader literature that supports the role of e-taxation in enhancing tax morale and reducing evasion through streamlined and automated services.

5.1 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings the study revealed that e-taxation has no significant positive effect on consolidated tax systems in Enugu State.

That e-taxation has significant positive effect on tax compliance rates among taxpayers in Enugu State.

5.2 Conclusion

The study examined e-taxation and revenue generation in Enugu State, with particular reference to how digital tools and platforms influenced revenue generation, taxpayers compliance and consolidated tax system. The findings revealed that e-taxation initiative has significantly enhanced the operational capacity of tax officials and revenue board, streamlining processes, reducing human interference and increasing access to tax services. Moreover, the digitization of tax administration and

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generating ideas, has led to improved accountability, reduced revenue leakages and foster greater public trust in the system. However, there are still hitches, in the area of consolidated tax system. Rating per head/business pattern among the informal sectors is a huge challenge as many are over taxed, while at some point some are under charged, lacking defined criteria in the tax system. Secondary, is the issue of double taxation, which e-taxation system stand to eliminate, yet is still posing, great threat to taxpayers and finally tax officials lack the basic knowledge on the new consolidated tax system in Enugu State.

5.2 Recommendation

1. A comprehensive awareness campaign should be launched to educate taxpayers on the benefits, procedures and usage of e-taxation platform, thereby increasing compliance and encourage popular participation, while a criteria for the consolidated tax system be defined, particularly among the informal sector.

2. A robust cybersecurity framework should be implemented to safeguard taxpayers' data, ensure system and integrity and build public trust in e-taxation initiatives

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